

University Student's Perspective on Convenient Food: With Special Reference to Bilaspur City Chhattisgarh

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Abstract:

Many students do not have time or cooking skills to prepare food especially students who live as tenants and paying guests. The students go for convenient food specially baked or fried food, partially cooked food, frozen items, beverages, and pre-cut sprouts and fruits. The main objectives of the paper are: to study types of convenient food, examine the drivers for the consumption of convenient food, also study students' preferences and buying behavior attitudes towards convenient food. The study is descriptive in nature and based on secondary data. A structured closed-ended questionnaire has been formed for University students. The questionnaire was filled out by 60 students to conduct this study. A bar graph has been used to show the preferences and answers to questions. The drivers of food consumption among students are food price the major economic driver influencing purchase decisions and consumption and the Physical environment (availability and accessibility of food products, food retail environments, and time).

Keywords: Convenient food, Physical environment, availability, and accessibility.

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1. INTRODUCTION: -Bilaspur is a district in Chhattisgarh state of India. This district is an education hub of this state. There are three universities in Koni, Bilaspur, Central University Guru Ghaisdas Vishwavidyalaya, State University Atal Bihari Vajpayee Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur and Pt Sundarlal Sharma Open University. Due to the presence of these 3 university students living in Koni, Bilaspur area as paying guests, take the room on rent sharing a room with friends. Because there is a limited seat in hostel. Students do not have good skills in cooking and do not have the time they prefer convenient food.

Schedules for students are busier than ever. Due to commuting, or attending lectures, practical's, and different classes like dance & music, more than one-third of students have less free time now than they did earlier.

Now students prefer to eat Spaghetti and naan bread pizzas. Cheese and ham, Jacket potato, chips, burgers, white bread, Bakery Products, Ice creams, Frozen Yoghurt etc.

Convenient food is food that requires little or no preparation and can be served hot or cold, these foods are easily portable, have long shelf life and students can save time. There is only one convenience store Reliance Fresh where the students get all types of convenient food. **Convenience stores** exist to sell products people want, at a location where they want to buy them. Convenient food is also grocery stores. Students love junk food. It is available, inexpensive, and designed to hit students' taste buds in a way that makes them crave more and more of it.

In today fast fast-paced life students go for convenient food. If they are getting ready meal after coming from college or university even if it is Maggie they will be delighted. It also saves time for cleaning and washing vegetables.

Advantages

- No/ Very less cooking skills required
- Preparation time is reduced
- Less waste
- Easily carry while travelling

Scope of the study

Urbanization and modernization changes life style of the students, now they are very busy and prefer junk food. These food are popular among students and demanded by them, they are easily available in the market. The study through light on how this food is an essential part of their life. The study also explain factor like taste, convenient to use and easily availability shift student eating habits towards convenient food. The study provides new insight into their perception and students' physiological mindset towards convenient food.

OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the paper are

1. To study types of convenient food.
2. To examine the drivers for the consumption of convenient food.
3. To investigate students' buying behavior attitudes and preferences towards convenient food.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marquis, Marie. (2005). the study evaluated the perception that eating well, having a varied diet, and maintaining weight were negatively correlated to convenience. Negative correlations were obtained between convenience and fresh vegetables, potatoes, eggs, fresh meat, fresh fish and fresh poultry, herbal tea, and alcohol.

Andrew S. Hanks, David R. Just, et.al. (2012)The study found that students increased their consumption of flavored milk, but flavored milk's share of total consumption did not increase.

Srinivasan, Sunder & Shende, Kiran. (2016). The study was conducted in different areas of Pune city This study has its focuses on understanding the benefits these working women would obtain through the utilization of convenience foods.

Sogari G, Velez-Argumedo C. (2018). The study highlighted the importance of consulting college students when developing healthy eating interventions across the campus (e.g., labeling healthy food options and information campaigns) and considering individual-level factors and socio-ecological aspects in the analysis.

Racine EF, Schorno R, Gholizadeh S. (2022). Multivariate analyses were used to examine demographic, economic, and behavioral factors associated with Student Average Fast-Food Health Scores. Being of a low income, spending more money on fast-food items, and having a lower GPA were associated with lower Student Average Fast-Food Health Scores.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is descriptive in nature. Three universities(Central University Guru Ghaisdas

Vishwavidyalaya, State University Atal Bihari Vajpayee Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur and Pt Sundarlal Sharma Open University) have been taken to conduct this study. A structured questionnaire was prepared which was filled by the 60 students who live as PG and in rental houses. The respondents rated the most appropriate parameter 1 and the least preferred parameter last number. Bar graph chart has been used for analysis of the respondents' answers.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING

1. To fulfill the objective 1. To study types of convenient food secondary data has been used.

Broadly categories in 3 categories

1. Ready to Eat

Food is consumed from the package with or without warming, thawing, and without preparation. It's popped into the oven for a few minutes, heated, and eaten.

1.1. Dairy items Snacks (cheese, butter, and ghee)

1.2. Sweets gulab jamun, soan papdi, other sweets like laddo, chikki

1.3. Bakery products – cake & biscuits

1.4. Fried snacks-chips

1.5. Frozen food-ice-cream, peas.

2. Ready to Use- Food needs some preparation like cooking, frying, and reconstitution before consumption. Under these categories we have

2.1. Ready to cook food such as Maggie, Idli, and dosa.

2.2. Ready to fry- papad, finger chips,

2.3. Breakfast cereals

2.4. Ready to constitute food

2.5. Masalas

2.6. fresh-cut vegetables

2.7. Canned food.

3. Beverages:-

3.1. Ready to serve – need some preparation before serving like Knorr soup

3.2. Ready to drink (drink directly consumed from the container like Sprite, Mazza) available in tetra packs.

Objective 2: To examine the drivers for the consumption of convenient food.

Rating scale has been used to conduct this objective student rate 1 for most appropriate parameter or drivers.

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Ok 4. Less Important

1. Mood

Table 1

Interpretation: - Most of the students agree that after the convenience food meal they will be satisfied. This divers change the student mood, they satisfied after having convenience food.

2. Convenience(Availability & Preparation)

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Ok 4. Less Important 5. Neutral

Table 2

Interpretation:- Convenience food is easy to prepare , followed by other drivers that it is easily available in shops are the main reason students prefer this food.

3. Sensory appeal

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Ok 4. Less Important

Table 3

Interpretation: -Students prefer convenience food because its taste is good and yummy, and look nice after cook.

4. Price

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Less Important

Table 4

Interpretation:-The main drivers, students consume convenience food is that this food is not expensive when students make it at home as compare to he buy the same food from market. Also from the above drivers after having this food student’s delight because food taste is good.

5. Ethical concern

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Ok 4. Less Important 5. Neutral

Table 5

Interpretation: -Students check before purchasing Expiry date and other details mention on packet, followed by Checked Food business operator has an authentic license by the Food Safety and Standard Act. (Brand).

3. Objective to investigate students' buying behavior attitudes and preferences towards convenient food.

3.1. When you buy convenient food

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Ok 4. Less Important

Table 6

Interpretation:- Students impulsive buying convenience food when they go for shopping or roaming around campus after college hours. They also rate that every month they buy convenience food though it become very popular among students.

3.2. Which convenience food you preferred to buy most of the time.

1. Most Important 2. Important 3. Ok

Table 7

Interpretation: - Among category of convenient foods, mostly students beverages (soft drink, buttermilk, lassie and other packaged drink). Followed by ready to eat food like biscuits, cake & chips.

5. CONCLUSION

Convenience foods were developed to make our lives easier. They reduce the amount of time spent home cooking meals grocery shopping, and preparing food, as well as fewer leftovers (with single-portion foods) and easier cleanup.

The drivers of food consumption among students are food price is the major economic drivers influencing purchase decisions and consumption and Physical environment (availability and accessibility of food products, food retail environments, time).

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